

Robo2D Soccer Simulation Team Description Paper

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Abstract. This article contains descriptions of the activities of the Robo2D soccer 2D simulation team. This year, our team tried to increase the accuracy of both defense and offense, decision, managing and etc. strategies. So, we developed our ideas by designing and developing algorithms. Here are some of these algorithms and solutions.

Keywords: RoboCup. Soccer 2D simulation. Conditional decision. Machine Learning

1 Introduction

Robo2D soccer simulation team was founded 1 year ago. We started coding on Cyrus Base¹ and developed the base code. We tried to use machine learning in our team with using Keras but it doesn't helpful for us. So, we used Cyrus Base defaults.

1.1 Related Work

Our team used some wonderful and good ideas from the other teams in recent years. For example, we used an algorithm that like Cyrus 2014 Marking Algorithm that they published on their GitHub [1] and Hades Marking [2]. Also, we used Hades2D Shoot Action [3]. We used Formation Detector of Cyrus Team [4], Glider2D[5] and Fractals[6] Stamina managing and HillStone 2019 [7] Formation Type.

2 Strategies

In our experiences we know that players cannot find their position with thinking and we have to choose a rule for each player so we use Helios Base [8] Defaults and formation editor(fedit2) [9] source for make formation files with a bit change like HillStone 2019 [7]. Helios Base Goalie wasn't good for catching balls. So, we write an algorithm for goalie to change his position by configures when ball is close to our Goal instead thinking about if ball is shot find intersection of ball and Goalie Y (Figure 1). And now for stamina managing we code like Glider v.1.1 in Glider2D[5] and Fractals 2019[6]

Fig. 1. Goalie Formation using Helios Base formation Editor [9]

¹ Cyrus Base , https://github.com/cyrus2d/cyrus2d_base.git

3 Decisions

For Decision we used Helios Base Defaults ³. But in Jiling Base ⁴ we use configure files for decisions and it could be change in game cycles, so that is really good algorithm for machine learning and team experience. Also for extra Decisions we have written a library and use it in our teams.

4 Pass Strategy

As we mentioned above, we had a library for extra decisions and some important Decisions. Players think Sensitivity of Situation with many parameters and choose best pass type for Pass and set variables with low or high sensitivity, because Helios Base Defaults for Pass was focus on side attack and that was helpless.

5 Through Pass

We used a Voronoi Diagram algorithm such as Glider2D[10] for Through Pass Decision (Figure 2). It imagine lots of Area of Ground, If in sides of ground opponent player detected, player ignoring to pass to player who are in side of ground.

Fig. 2. Simple Voronoi Diagram

6 Dribble

Our team considered three types for Dribble. Every Player who can kicking will decide and choose one of these types. If opponent player blockade kicker it chooses small and dodge and if kicker has enough space for dribble, he will dribble without dodge in a longer distance than small Dribble type. We called this type Self-Pass. But if kicker cannot decide in these situations, he going to doing a normal Dribble.

Table 1. Dribble Types

Name	Dodge	Blockade Situation
Small	Yes	Yes
Self-Pass	No	No
Normal	-	-

³ Helios Base Decisions, https://github.com/helios-base/helios-base/blob/master/src/bhv_basic_move.cpp, https://github.com/helios-base/helios-base/blob/master/src/bhv_basic_offensive_kick.cpp, https://github.com/helios-base/helios-base/blob/master/src/bhv_goalie_basic_move.cpp

⁴ Jiling Base, <https://github.com/RSQLCGROUP/Jiling-Base.git>

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